

A new subspecies of *Dorcadion* (*Carinatodorcadion*) *fulvum* (Scopoli, 1763) from Odessa Region, Ukraine (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)

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Abstract

Dorcadion (*Carinatodorcadion*) *fulvum odessum* ssp. n. very close to the nominative subspecies is described from Ukraine (Odessa environs)

Key words

Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, new subspecies, taxonomy, zoogeography.

Introduction

Dorcadion (*Carinatodorcadion*) *fulvum* (Scopoli, 1763) is a very common species in south-eastern Europe. It was represented up to now by 3 subspecies: nominative subspecies (Figs 1-5) is distributed in Western Adriatic (Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Macedonia, Albania), Bulgaria and Hungary; *D. (C.) f. erythropterum* Fischer von Waldheim, 1823 (Figs 6-9) (= *D. f. opillicum* Zamoroka, 2021) is distributed in Ukraine, Moldova, Poland, Rumania, Czechia, Slovakia, Austria, European Turkey; *D. (C.) f. heracles* Vartanis, 2024 (Figs 10-11) is known from Greece. Below a new taxon is described from South West Ukraine.

Material and methods

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia)

ML - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia)

SM - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow, Russia)

Taxonomical part

Family Cerambycidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Lamiinae Latreille, 1825

Tribe Dorcadionini Swainson, 1840

Genus *Dorcadion* Dalman, 1817a: 397

Type species: *Cerambyx glycyrrhizae* Pallas, 1773

Subgenus *Carinatodorcadion* Breuning, 1943

Type species: *Cerambyx carinatus* Pallas, 1771

***Dorcadion* (*Carinatodorcadion*) *fulvum odessum* ssp. n.**

Figs 12-13

Dorcadion fulvum erythropterum, Zamoroka & Olbrycht, 2021: 1, 4, part. – “Ukraine: Berezivka, Odesa Region”.

Type material

Holotype male (Fig. 12), Ukraine, Odessa Region, Berezovka environs, platform 1214 km [47°11'19.36"N, 30°54'31.62"E], 15.5.2013, G. Demidov leg. - ML; 117 paratypes; 23 males, 10 females with same label - ML; 16 males, 13 females with same label - MD; 29 males, 25 females, Ukraine, Odessa Region, Berezovka environs, 21.5.2013, G. Demidov leg. - ML; 1 male, Ukraine, Odessa Region, Ananiev District [now Podolsk District], Dolinskoe, 2-3.4.2002, S. Vashchenko leg. - SM.

Diagnosis

Body very narrow; head black, relatively small; frons slightly transverse, a little depressed along central suture, with narrow smooth and shining cuticle along its both sides, with scattered rugose punctation and dense, velvety black pubescence laterally; genae relatively

wide, about 1.5 times narrower than lower eye lobes; antennae black, with red 1st joint; 1st joint with short scattered strong setae, becoming longer at joint apex; basal antennal joints shining, apical joints looking mat because of micropubescence; prothorax black, in males a little shorter than its basal width, in females – rather shorter, with well-developed lateral tubercles; pronotum with very rough punctation, with deep central furrow, followed by smooth lines; elytra very narrow; in males about 2.0-2.3 times longer than central width, in females - about 1.6-1.9 times; brown, shining, sometimes with black areas in anterior humeral portions; scattered elytral punctation concentrated along suture; elytral furrows usually indistinct, but in certain females moderately developed because humeral depression can be well pronounced; legs reddish; last abdominal tergites rounded; body length in males: 15.2-17.5 mm, width: 4.3-5.0 mm; body length in females: 15.9-18.6 mm; width: 5.2-6.6 mm.

Differential diagnosis

The new subspecies is much closer to the narrow smooth nominative subspecies from the Western Adriatic than to wide and roughly sculptured *D. f. erythropterum* Fischer von Waldheim, 1823 from Eastern Europe, who has rather wide body in males and females, deep furrows along center of frons and pronotum, usually well-developed elytral furrows; more roughly sculptured pronotum and elytra. The new taxon differs from the nominative subspecies by sharp pronotal tubercles and wider central pronotal furrow which is accompanied by wider smooth stripes.

Distribution

Odessa Region, Ukraine.

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Figs 1-5. *D. (C.) f. fulvum*: 1 - male, Serbia, Zrenjanin, D. Chomprag; 2 - male, Bulgaria N, Lom Cherkovna vill. 270 m, VI.2010, T. Ljubomirov; 3 - female, Bulgaria N, Lom Cherkovna vill., 397 m, 21.V.2011, T. Ljubomirov. *D. (C.) f. erythropterum*: 4 - male, Ukraine, Kyiv, 11.6.1980; 5 - female, Zaporozhye, Khortitsa, 12.5.1983, A. Zhakov.

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PARATYPUS 3

Dorcadion fulvum
opillicum ssp. nov.
A. Zamoroka

Kuropatnyky,
Halych.dstr., Iv.-Frank,
Ukraine, 19.VI.2015
A. Zamoroka

male

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PARATYPUS 8

Dorcadion fulvum
opillicum ssp. nov.
A. Zamoroka

'KasovaHra',
Burshtyn, Iv.-Frankiv.,
Ukraine, 01.V.2014
A. Zamoroka

female

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Figs 6-9. *D. (C.) f. erythropterum*: 6, 8 - paratypes (male and female) of *D. f. opillicum* Zamoroka, 2021; 7, 9 - labels of the paratypes;

Figs 10-13. *D. (C.) f. heracles*: 10 - paratype, male, Greece, Pieria Province, Olympos Mt., 2021, J. Vartanis.; 11 - paratype, female with the same label. *D. (C.) f. odessum* ssp. n.: 12 - holotype, male, Ukraine, Odessa Region, Berezovka environs, platform 1214 km, 15.5.2013, G. Demidov leg.; 13 - paratype, female with same label.